

A STUDY ON FARMER PREFERENCE TOWARDS NEW PADDY HYBRID VNR MINIBHOG IN NIRMAL
DISTRICT OF TELANGANA

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Abstract

Rice is the second most important cereal crop grown throughout the world and occupies around 90 thousand acres of land in Nirmal district of Telangana. Therefore there is a great potential for seed production here and hence private sector has emerged as a dominant player in the seed industry in this state. The main objectives of the study were to analyse farmer expectation towards paddy hybrid seeds, identify source of information, analyse fine varieties cultivated by farmers and assess the marketable surplus in fine segment of paddy. Data was collected from 117 farmers through purposive sampling technique. The findings revealed that there was no much marketable surplus during the Kharif season and Aman fine variety of paddy was mostly cultivated. Most of the farmers expected seeds to be disease resistant and 56.41 per cent of the farmers were aware of VNR seeds through field demo method of promotional activity and preferred this brand of seeds for its higher yield.

Keywords: Seed industry, Paddy hybrid seed, Promotional activities, Brand awareness

Introduction

Seed is the basic and most vital input for sustainable agriculture. Total production of the quality seed alone is 15-20 percent based on the crop which is estimated to arouse up to 45 percent, if are managed efficiently (Singh *et al.* 2019). The Indian seed sector made a headway towards multifarious industry with the entanglement of large number of private firms and increasing prominence on research and development activities. A major re-structuring of the seed industry by Government of India after the national seed project came into existence (Seednet.gov.in). Increase in the production of agricultural crops depends on the production of good quality seeds and on the coherence of regulated flow of seeds reaching farmers on time. Indian seed industry, over the years experienced a metamorphosis by adapting and innovating upon the scientific advancements in variety development and quality seed production.

Rice is the second most important cereal crop grown throughout the world and it is an important staple food crop cultivated across the country, accounting for more than 40 percent of the country's food grain production (Singh 2019). In order to meet the demand of the increasing population, the present-day production of 416 lakh MT (India Agristat 2019) of rice has to be increased. Kumar *et al.*, (2009) estimated that the total domestic consumption of rice by 2021-22 would be around 1133 lakh MT's. They also opined that by 2021-22, yield of rice must further be improved to 2.65 t/ha. It is rather difficult to achieve this target with the present day inbred varieties. Therefore, to sustain self-sufficiency in rice, additional production of 1.5 million tons is needed every year. Among the limited options, hybrid technology is the one of the proven methods that is currently available for stepping up rice production significantly. Hybrid rice technology was the most feasible and readily adoptable which was amply demonstrated in China (Nirmala *et al.* 2013).

The rice hybrids, recently introduced in cultivation, on an average, give 10 to 15 q/ha additional yield over the conventional varieties (about 20 percent increase). Therefore, introduction of hybrids and popularisation of their production technology are feasible and readily adoptable to achieve targeted production (Singh *et al.* 2019).

Andhra Pradesh accounts for 7.49 million tons of rice production in India, with an area of 2.16 million hectares under rice cultivation. In India, major rice producing states are West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, etc (India Today September 18 2018). Telangana has about nearly 40+ lakh acres under rice cultivation, (Telangana Today April 13 2020) which is mostly irrigated. Area under paddy cultivation in this Kharif season is expected to be around 49.3 lakh acres (Telangana Today 14 May 2020). Major constraints in rice production are bacterial leaf blight, brown plant hopper, smut diseases, rice blast and micro nutrient deficiencies. In Nirmal district of Telangana, paddy is produced in around 90 thousand acres of land (Dept of Agriculture Telangana

2019). Telangana is the seed hub of the country for production of various crop seeds. It produces about 37.00 lakh quintals of seeds in an area of 3.22 lakh acres. There is a great potential for seed production in Telangana. Hybrid paddy seed is produced in Karimnagar and Warangal districts (Agricultural Challenges and Way Forward 2014).

In India, there are many private agri-input companies playing significant role in rice seed business. Many seed companies are based out of Nirmal district and are creating awareness about their products to attract new customers. A number of seed producing companies, including multinationals, have entered the seed market in the state. Companies like Bayer crop sciences, Pro Agro, Nuziveedu Seeds Ltd., Advanta India Ltd, Emergent Geneues Ltd, Nath seeds, VNR seeds are now engaged in evolving new private hybrids of paddy, cotton, chillies and other vegetable crops. Thus, private sector has emerged as a dominant player in the seed industry in Telangana.

This study focuses on finding the effective promotional activities and brand awareness of fine varieties of new paddy hybrid VNR MINIBHOG in the Nirmal District of Telangana State. The main objectives of this study were to analyse farmer expectation towards paddy hybrid seeds and identify various sources of information on paddy hybrid seeds. It also aimed at analysing fine varieties cultivated by farmers and assessing the marketable surplus in fine segment of paddy in the study area. The study also sheds light on awareness and preference of paddy farmers on VNR seeds. Effectiveness of promotional activities of hybrid seed companies in influencing farmers to buy a particular brand of paddy hybrid seeds was also evaluated in this study.

Methodology

Nirmal District of Telangana State was selected for this study, with a sample of 117 farmers through purposive sampling technique. Primary data was collected from farmers through a well-structured and pre-tested questionnaire. Secondary data pertaining to the study was collected from official websites, magazines, books, journals, company's data, and past research work. The data collected was then analysed using percentage analysis, bar graphs and pie charts. Also, marketable surplus was calculated using the following formula;

$$\text{Marketable Surplus} = P - C$$

Where,

P = Total Production,

C = Consumption for home needs, seeds, etc.

Major Findings

The data collected from the sample farmers was subjected to analysis and the results are presented and discussed in this section

Land Holdings

Data on handlings of sample respondents as collected analysed and presented in Table I.

Table I. Land holdings of Paddy Growers in Nirmal district

S. No.	Land Holdings of the Respondents	No. of Sample Respondents	Percentage to Total
1.	Small and Marginal (< 2 ha.)	47	40.17
2.	Medium (2 – 4 ha.)	43	36.75
3.	Large (> 4 ha.)	27	23.08
	Total	117	100

Majority of the sample respondents in Nirmal district were small and marginal farmers with a land holding of less than 2 hectares (40.17 per cent) and only 23.08 per cent of the farmers had more than 4 hectares of land.

Farmer Expectation towards paddy hybrid seeds

Farmers' expectation towards paddy hybrid seeds in the study area is presented in Table II

Table II. Farmer Expectation towards Paddy Hybrid Seeds in Nirmal District

S. No.	Farmer Expectations	No. of Sample Respondents	Percentage to Total
1.	Disease Resistance	32	27.35
2.	Diseases Resistance + Early Maturity	5	4.27
3.	Disease Resistance + High Yield	48	41.02
4.	High Yield + Early Maturity	8	6.83
5.	Early Maturity Varieties	7	5.98
6.	High Yield	14	11.97
7.	Others	3	2.58
	Total	117	100

Most of the farmers (41.02 per cent) expected features such as disease resistance & high yield from paddy hybrid seeds followed by 27.35 per cent of the farmers who expected only disease resistance, and 11.97 percent of the farmers who expected high yield (Table I). About 2.58 per cent of farmers had other expectations like resistance to lodging, low cutting rate and new varieties.

Source of Information

Information for the paddy growers were majorly from three sources i.e., existing farmers, dealers and demo plots. Farmers received information either from these three sources or a combination of these.

Table III. Source of Information available to Paddy Farmers

S. No.	Source of Information	No. of Sample Respondents	Percentage to Total
1.	Existing farmers + Demo plot	09	7.69
2.	Existing farmer + Dealer	20	17.09
3.	Existing farmer + Company Representative	08	6.84
4.	Existing farmer	19	16.24
5.	Dealer + Demo plot	11	9.40
6.	Dealer + Field day	07	5.98
7.	Dealer + Company representative	17	14.53
8.	Dealer	08	6.84
9.	Demo plot + Company representative	03	2.56
10.	Demo plot	15	12.82
	Total	117	100.00

From the Table III, it can be inferred that most of the farmers (17.09 per cent) gathered information from the existing farmers and dealers regarding the paddy information, 16.23 per cent from existing farmers as the influence of peers was high and they trusted their co-farmers more. About 14.52 per cent of the farmers were influenced by the dealers and company representatives in availing the information regarding paddy hybrid seeds, and demo plot technique (12.82 per cent) also had a good influence in convincing farmers as

'Seeing is Believing'. It was a practical technique where the companies gave the farmer's their seed for free of cost, therefore giving them a real time experience in using their paddy hybrid seeds.

Fine Varieties of Paddy cultivated

The different fine varieties of paddy cultivated in Nirmal district are represented in Table IV.

Table IV. Fine Varieties of Paddy cultivated in Nirmal District

S. No.	Brand of Fine Variety	No. of Sample Respondents	Percentage to Total
1.	Jai Sri Ram	15	24.19
2.	Aman	16	25.08
3.	Raithu Mithra	8	12.90
4.	Kunaram	3	4.83
5.	1008	3	4.83
6.	Kaveri Chintu	2	3.22
7.	JK	2	3.22

8.	Siri	3	4.83
9.	Others	10	16.12
Total		62	100

From the above Table IV, it is clearly evident that majority of the farmers cultivated Aman variety (25.81 per cent), followed by Jai Sri Ram variety (24.19 percent). Aman variety and Jai Sri Ram were cultivated more as they belong to super fine segment and the price paid to those varieties were high. About 12.90 per cent of the farmers cultivated Raithu Mitra variety of fine rice, and varieties like Kunaram, 1008 and Sri constituted to 4.84 per cent each. JK and Kaveri Chintu were the least cultivated varieties (3.23 per cent). The other fine varieties cultivated by the sample respondents were

Kamakshi, Ankur, Chetana, Kisangold, Chandana, Megha, Navya, Nuziveedu, Savitri and Sindhu. However, they constituted to a much lesser share in comparison to the above listed varieties.

Marketable Surplus in Fine Segment Paddy

It was evident that majority of the farmers weremarginal and small farmers (Table I). Even if the farmer cultivated fine varieties, it would be cultivated on a small pieceof land which was sufficient for his own consumption and his family members.

Table V. Marketable surplus in Fine Segment Paddy in Nirmal District

S. No.	Farmer Category	Total Production (per acre)	Produce Retained fordifferent purpose	Marketable Surplus
1.	Small and Marginal	12 qt.	7 qt.	5 qt.
2.	Medium	24 qt.	12 qt.	12 qt.
3.	Large	25 qt.	15 qt.	10 qt.

If a marginal farmer cultivated fine varieties, i.e. on his 2.5 acres of land, 0.5 acre of land was cultivated for fine varieties which would yield an average of 12qtl /0.5 acre, from which 7 qt. was required for his own family consumption and the marketable surplus would be 5 qt (Table V). From this, it could be concluded that no much marketable surplus of the paddy was available during the kharif season.

Sirisha and Babu (2014) reported that the companies were unable to convince farmers in opting for their high yielding seeds due to the cheap or fake brands present in market, hence proper awareness should be created by giving a sample of their seeds to farmers, so on seeing the result they could go for quality seeds.

The degree to which the sample farmers were aware of VNR paddy hybrid Minbhog was analysed and presented in Fig I.

Awareness of Farmers on VNR seeds

Figure I. Awareness of Farmers on VNR Paddy Hybrid Seeds

From Fig I, it could be inferred that 56.41 per cent of farmers were aware of VNR seeds and 43.59 per cent of the farmers were not aware of VNR seeds in the paddy segment. VNR were popular in the horticultural segment, especially vegetables, as they were high

yielders and, had a good growth and germination percentage.

Preference of VNR seeds

The reasons for preferring VNR paddy seeds by the farmers were collected and are presented in Fig II.

Figure II. Preference of Paddy farmers on VNR seeds

It can be observed from Figure II, that about 46.97 per cent of the farmers preferred hybrid paddy varieties from VNR for its higher yield, when compared to indigenous varieties, followed by disease resistance quality (33.33 per cent). Product offering like disease

resistance, reduced the cost of cultivation, thereby giving increased profits to the farmers. About 19.70 per cent of the farmers preferred hybrid paddy seeds from VNR for its superior quality in terms good growth and germination percentage.

Effectiveness of Promotional Activities

Promotional activities help the company to communicate about their products and services offered to customers. It helps in creating awareness among potential consumers of their product, draw their attention towards their product and create an impulse to buy their product. Chirwa *et al.* (2007) used grocery shops, rural traders, extension agents, health clinics, and NGOs for intensified variety promotion through publicity, using posters, leaflets, brochures and radio messages. These activities were carried out in close

collaboration with farmers, NGOs, extension agencies, village traders and various other institutions.

VNR has adopted several promotional activities like farmers meeting, demos on field, organizing field days, etc. to create awareness and promote their product to their target customers. Various promotional activities of VNR Company in promoting their hybrid paddy seeds in Nirmal district was analysed and is presented in Fig III.

Figure III. Promotional

Activities by VNR in Nirmal District

From Figure III, it could be inferred that from the various promotional activities carried out by VNR seeds; demo field, farmers meeting, field day and a combination of these three activities influenced the farmers to buy from their brand. Demo field influenced the farmers more (50.43 per cent) especially when the company had newly launched its products in the Nirmal district of Telangana, followed by a combination of demo field & farmer meeting (29.91 per cent), combination of demo field & field day (12.82 per cent) and farmer meetings (5.13 per cent). Remaining 1.71 per cent of the farmers were influenced by field day activities.

Conclusion

Most of the farmers expected disease resistance and high yield from the paddy hybrid seeds as it reduced cost incurred on pest and disease management and gave higher yield that increased the revenue of the farmers. VNR Minibhog was a suitable product, as it was tolerant to BPH, blight and gave high yield compared to other fine varieties cultivated in the study area. About 60 per cent of the farmers cultivated fine varieties which were mostly for the household consumption. VNR Minibhog was suitable for both the purposes i.e. household consumption and as a marketable product. VNR Company should increase its market penetration by influencing their existing farmer base and promote their product by word of mouth, as the farmers trusted their peers, than any other source of information. The company should try to utilise their brand image in vegetable seeds, and promote its hybrid seed varieties in paddy fine segment also. The company should conduct more demo plots and provide free samples to the farmers initially in order to establish themselves in the paddy hybrid seeds segment in Nirmal district. It should also provide consistent support and advisory services to the farmers post their purchase of seeds from their brand.

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